

TURKISH FOLK TALES AND KARAKALPAK FOLKLORE.

Sultanova Jazira Berdaxovna

Doctoral student of Nukus State Pedagogical Institute

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Abstract. *This article gives an overview of Turkish folk tales and Karakalpak folklore. The formation of the national literature of any nation is carried out in close connection with the culture, history and literature of neighboring peoples. These issues were covered during the article.*

Keywords: *Turkish folk tales, Karakalpak folklore, literature, history, Karakalpak literature.*

ТУРЕЦКИЕ НАРОДНЫЕ СКАЗКИ И КАРАКАЛПАКСКИЙ ФОЛЬКЛОР.

Аннотация. *В этой статье дается обзор турецких народных сказок и каракалпакского фольклора. Формирование национальной литературы любого народа осуществляется в тесной связи с культурой, историей и литературой соседних народов. Эти вопросы были затронуты в ходе статьи.*

Ключевые слова: *турецкие народные сказки, каракалпакский фольклор, литература, история, каракалпакская литература.*

The formation of the national literature of any nation takes place in close connection with the culture, history, and literature of neighboring nations. The history of these relations, the literary examples of the early ages, the spiritual culture of the peoples of the left world, and the best examples of the human mind, are an inseparable part of the cultural connection and literary relations. go and plant your own people the best, most powerful mouth is throwing the jets of two arrows.

The historical pattern of Karakalpak literature appeared both in the development of Karakalpak folklore and through the creation methods of folklore of world literature, the development of the most powerful plot connections, unique forms of folklore, the genre of world folklore. Such similarities and plot connections found their solutions in the appearance and content of the literary and cultural connections between the folk tales of the Turkic peoples.

Tales became a separate genre of folklore and became a unique content and a form of its own. Its content does not have a certain norm, it is a collection of mythological pictures, stories dedicated to life, fantasy-fantasy plots, stories that cannot be imagined in real life.

Turkish folk tales are told from the most important parts of Turkish folklore, plot constructions have all kinds of forms, Northern synthesizes the folkloric and literary traditions of the Western peoples from the plots, and the unique characters of Turkish tales are distinctly different from the tales of other peoples.

Based on the characteristics of Turkish folk tales, the main characters of Turkish folk tales are based on a specific motif, and they can be divided into two groups: fairy tales (magical) and folk tales (household). old It shows itself in the work of the neighbor of the two topars.

One of the main heroes of Turkic tales, like the tales of the peoples of the world, is a giant. In most of the folk tales, Giants-Turk appears as a human-loving creature, in some places it takes on the human form, while in other stories it is depicted as a creature flying in the sky, possessing amazing powers and miraculous actions. If fairy tales appear in male form in Turkish fairy tales,

they have the idea that they supply water with the construction of large palaces, as well as mountain caves and vast groves. Fairy-Iranian language unity and image, it is close to humanity, it appears in many fairy tales in the form of one fairy, seven fairy, forty fairy, and gives wonderful help to the heroes of fairy tales who are in trouble. The third image is the mother of the goddess, who is depicted in fairy tales as a priestess, who blindfolded and has the power to turn a person into an animal and an animal into a person. The plots of this character are depicted in the epics, fairy tales, legends and mythology of the Karakalpak folklore, like the peoples of the world, in artistic imagery, with the colorful colors of the characters.

presented in the most mature way. For example: Alpamis in the "Alpamis" saga, when he was looking for his bride Barshinay, he met a scheming drunkard near the black house, and was deceived by her words and fell into the dungeon of the black house; In the "Koblan" epic, Koblan's journey to the Barsakelmes country, his encounters with the giant, his journey of forty days and forty nights on the road; The story of Anjim in the "Sharyar" epic, when he was on his way to Gohikap mountain in search of his brother Sharyar, he met a drunken old woman, he overcame the advice given by a ghostly fairy on the way, and brought his brother Sharyar back to a human form from a place where he was stone and ice. It has a place in the world treasure, maybe we will compare the plots with the participation of certain characters...

The compositional structure of Turkish fairy tales is very unique, and its performers are distinguished by their skill. For example: the beginning of Turkish fairy tales begins with "There is one, there is no one, in the old days..." (Gurring about weeping pomegranate, laughing quince), (Tale about water-carrying beauty), (Tale about Alitenz), The completion of the tale is "...he achieved his dreams..." (The Tale of the King's Child), (The Fisherman's Child), "...he achieved his goal..." (The Tale of the One Dervish) to the methods of execution of Karakalpak tales. is coming close. Also, in Turkish fairy tales, there are a lot of idioms of exaggeration and similarities in regular word sequences: "He devours when he chews", "He lit a fire on his head", "The world dances from his eyes", "He looked double because of his fear", "He hurried until his tongue was stuck in his throat", " He lost his mind", "Forty days, forty nights lying in sleep...", "From eye to eye", "Shame was visible on his face" and others.

If the content of Turkish folk tales, the events of the era of Islam in the majority of the world are shown in the actions of the characters, in Karakalpak folklore, such events are related to the religion of Islam. Today, after the book "Quran-kerim" of the prophet Muhammed, the world of Islam, the world of Arabs, in the world of Islam, there are a lot of things that are related to nature, fantasy mythology, prayer, and Zoroastrianism was, use Turkish fairy tales, in the middle of historical times, seem to be playing in the background...

The examples we have given from the fairy tales are dark from the river, and if we look at his Turkin, the culture, literature and folklore of the Turkish peoples will become more vivid.